

Productivity and wage effects of managerial characteristics and Iso9001 certification in Italy

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Introduction

An increasing polarization between technological laggards and leaders is emerging in the population of firms of OECD countries, causing skewness in growth rate distributions (Foster et al., 2019; Corrado et al., 2021). In the case of the Italian economy, Dosi et al. (2021) formulated a neo-dualist hypothesis, where high-performance firms co-exist with a large population exhibiting stagnant productivity levels, modest profits, and low wages paid to the workers. In this study, I analyse if specific managerial characteristics and practices (such as the Iso9001 certification) help laggard firms close the gap regarding productivity and wages with the leaders. The empirical analysis I perform here relies on a broader research project (H2020 Untangled) in which a distance-to-frontier framework (DTF) has been applied to investigate whether the introduction of specific technologies or managerial practices helps the laggards shorten the distance between them and the companies at the frontier (Pompei and Venturini, 2022).

Methods (max 100 words)

According to Andrews et al. (2019), I apply a DTF approach by means of a pooled OLS; next, I take into account unobserved heterogeneity of firms and potential endogeneity between the Iso9001 certification and outcomes (multifactor productivity, profits and average wages), by performing a difference-in-difference estimation with fixed effects model (Autor, 2003).

Results

Companies adopting innovative managerial practices such as Iso9001 certification are found to close the gap more easily, not only in terms of productivity but also in terms of profits and average wages.

These results are robust when we address endogeneity issues by performing a Diff-in-Diff fixed effects regression, especially for productivity and profits. Interestingly, the positive effect of the Iso9001 scheme on these two dimensions of performance shows up slowly, i.e. with some lags with respect to the introduction of this practice. The gap-reducing

effect of Iso9001 certification on average wages paid by leaders and laggard firms is not confirmed in the Diff-in-Diff specification.

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